

EMERGENCE AND DEVELOPMENT OF PAINTING ART IN OUR COUNTRY

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Abstract. *This article discusses the emergence of painting art in our country, its development, scientists contributing to painting art, and the role and importance of painting art.*

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In the centuries-old historical development of our people, decorative art is the main part of our cultural heritage and values. A number of types of applied art, which arose, flourished and developed in the Uzbek land, are known to the world for their incomparable and uniqueness. When we think about this stage of development, we witness that the origin of Uzbek applied decorative art goes back to the early childhood of humanity, that is, to the time of the primitive community.

Many findings and monuments obtained as a result of archaeological excavations carried out for the purpose of scientific and analytical studies on the land of our country testify that the human activity of creating another object based on the artistic treatment of an object began in the Stone Age and continued for centuries to the present day. is coming.

In this place, the material evidence of the primitive community structure has reached us - work and hunting tools, household items and decorative items, and the remains of places where people lived. The remains of human and animal bodies, all kinds of pictures and bas-reliefs painted on the walls of caves and cellars are historical monuments that have remained under the soil for many centuries and are an important source of studying the history of primitive communities.

Painting became widespread in the New Stone (Neolithic) age, greatly influenced and helped the development of other types of decorative arts. Decorating pottery and other items with patterns became widespread. Parallel, spiral and wavy lines, circles formed the basis of many patterns of this period. Geometric patterns were gradually enriched and expanded in content by stylizing forms taken from the human, animal and plant world in a schematic way. Its elements began to reflect the symbolic signs of cosmic forces. For example, a socket is a symbol of the sun, a wavy line is a movement, a symbol of water, etc.

The art of painting now not only fulfills the function of decoration, but at the same time, it also began to express people's ideological and philosophical concepts.

Pottery developed further in Central Asia during the Bronze Age. The emergence of pottery looms ensured that the created items became more elegant and beautiful. The pottery found in Chust with pictures and patterns painted on a red background with black paint is noteworthy.

In the Iron Age, applied decorative arts took a leading place. In addition to geometric patterns, the use of plot4 compositions is especially developed in decoration works. In the study of the art and culture of the ancient period of Central Asia, samples of various applied decorative arts, weapons of war, hunting and work, found underground and in graves, play an important role. The surfaces of ceramics, bronze, gold, and silver items used for human needs are decorated with patterns, embossed images and sculptures. Life events are depicted on the surface of some objects.

These evidential materials serve to know the art and culture of the past, the aesthetic and artistic views of people.

It is known from archaeological excavations in Uzbekistan that the art of painting developed in Khorezm, Sogd, Bactria and other regions. The remains of paintings and patterns found in the excavations of Buddhist temples of Fayoztepa (I-II century) and Dalvarzintepa (I century) in Surkhandarya region are a clear proof of this.

In the understanding of the artistic life and culture of Central Asia in the IV-VI centuries BC, the "Amu Darya Wealth" (Ox Wealth) found in the upper reaches of the Amudarya River occupies an important place. Among these monuments, which are now kept in the British Museum in London, are noteworthy golden statues, various jugs, bracelets, rings, seals, coins, golden chariots and weapons.

So, it is no exaggeration to say that the art of painting was created by our ancestors who lived in our country from time immemorial, improved over time and discovered its current form.

The art of artistic painting is gaining a wide range even today without losing its position. Through the press, radio, television, cinema, people get acquainted with these art examples and their folk masters. Among these artists are O. Kasimjonov, Ye. Raufov, A. Boltayev, S. Norkoziyev, A. Azimov, A. Isayev, B. Abdullayev, T. Tokhtaho'jayev, J. Khakimov, Z. Bositkhanov. , M. Torayev, T. Ahmedov, K. Karimov, A. Ilhomov and others.

The works of our national masters and their apprentices can be seen in the Museum of Applied Arts in Tashkent, in exhibition halls, art salons, as well as in residential and public buildings, for example, Tashkent State Circus, Alisher Navoi Opera and Ballet Theater, National Academic can be seen in administrative and domestic facilities such as drama theater, Temurilar 14 History Museum, Oliy Majlis and City Hall buildings, metro stations, hotels, etc. Currently, the task is to expand the network of clubs in schools and extracurricular institutions as much as possible. Studying the art of folk painting serves to develop artistic taste, hard work in students and acquire a number of useful knowledge and skills. It helps to identify and develop their creative abilities.

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